

Introduction Of Advanced Pedagogical And Information And Communication Technologies Into The Educational Process In Teaching Japanese Hieroglyphs

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Abstract: As globalization accelerates in all spheres of society, it is inevitable that the interest in learning foreign languages will grow at the level of demand. This creates the need to research effective methods of teaching foreign languages, including Japanese, and put them into practice. The article analyzes the experiences of several foreign scientists on the methodology of effective teaching of hieroglyphs

Key words: foreign languages, Japanese, hieroglyphics, mnemonic, morphemic unit, interactive games.

Introduction

The study of hieroglyphs has attracted the attention of researchers for a long time. It was suggested that hieroglyphs should be studied using imaginative memory and a system of memorizing words. In the early 1990s, for the first time, special attention was paid to the problem of teaching Japanese in foreign methods. The authors expressed different opinions on the effectiveness of learning methods based on rote memorization. [1; pp.25-44].

In the early 1990s, for the first time, special attention was paid to the problem of teaching Japanese to foreigners using foreign methods. Japanese as a foreign language has been taught for more than 20 years. According to M. Noguchi, the methodology of teaching Japanese characters to students who have not developed the concept of ideographic writing is often organized similarly to the educational process at the elementary level in ordinary Japanese schools [2]. However, D. Kess and Yu. Miyamoto, J. Hazig and other researchers argued that such mechanistic teaching methods are an ineffective tool for foreign speakers of hieroglyphic character and its system of morphemic units [3;-p.21]. Recently, this problem has been actively discussed among linguists. However, this situation is considered an important aspect from the point of view of educators (A. Lollini, F. Flaherty, E. Kawaguchi) and psychologists (M. Sugita, E. Okita, S. Matsubara, Yu. Miyamoto).

Methods

In addition, a number of techniques are being developed that will help increase vocabulary in a foreign language, develop reading comprehension skills, and express thoughts clearly and clearly in the process of written and oral communication. To do this, of course, it is important to master the lexical layer of each language. Several methods have been developed to master the lexical layer, and one of them is the mnemonic method. In order to master a foreign language at an ideal level, the educational process is organized according to many methods. As an example, methods of joint learning of a foreign language, online programs developed on the basis of information technologies for the formation of a culture of communication can be cited.

Results

Each language has its own characteristics, which are important when learning foreign languages. Based on the structure of the language, the right approach to it will help you learn the language effectively. Although modern communication methods are rationally used in teaching Japanese, it is believed that the use of innovative technologies to alleviate the existing difficulties of the language is in demand.

It is known that Japanese is considered one of the most difficult languages in the world. Its difficulty lies in the presence of hieroglyphic words in the language. Despite the fact that Japanese language experts have created several innovations in terms of effective teaching of hieroglyphic words, there is a need to improve its teaching system.

The study and application of Japanese characters based on a unified writing system began to emerge at the end of the 20th century.

According to U. P. Strizhak's dissertation, the language unit in the teaching methodology of Japanese characters was not considered separately. Therefore, paying attention to this problem, he recommended paying attention to the following issues for the effective study of hieroglyphs as a single linguistic unit in the methodology of teaching Japanese hieroglyphs:

1. The development of morphemic skills among students in the correct use of the type of reading ON and the type of reading KUN of each hieroglyph.
2. Memorize the independent expression of the semantic meaning of each hieroglyph, the formation of a whole word by combining with other hieroglyphs and the interpretation of the meanings of an existing hieroglyphic word.
3. Formation of the skill of writing each character and using it in writing.

Also, in the process of studying Japanese hieroglyphs, he analysed the level of complexity of 3 types of topics that are currently considered relevant.

Discussion

Difficulties in reading hieroglyphic symbols were explained as follows:

- unlike the fact that reading is a type of speech activity, the presence of two or more types of reading each hieroglyph creates the need to memorize a large number of graphic and morphemic combinations;

- one of the difficulties in understanding the meaning of a hieroglyphic sign is explained by the fact that the written sign has an unusual semantic part and the multiplicity of the semantic meaning of each hieroglyph;

- the difficulty of correctly spelling a hieroglyphic word in the order of the specified sequence. Writing the same information over and over again to develop skills.

In addition, several works have been carried out on effective teaching of Japanese characters. For example, this can be observed in such works as "Introduction to the course of hieroglyphs" and "Methods of teaching hieroglyphs", created by N. G. Payusova. In this study, methods of teaching and fixing hieroglyphs were analysed and, mainly based on two methods, he made a comparative analysis of the study of hieroglyphs and gave an opinion on understanding the intuitive and analytical approach of the mind [4; – p.32].

At the same time, V. F. Rezanenko's psycholinguistic research is of great importance. In it, he explained the etymological, that is, the origin of six thousand hieroglyphs in harmony with semantic elements. In this way, the problem of mastering hieroglyphs is solved by systematizing the connection of a hieroglyph with an ideographic sign and its semantic part.

Japanese scientist Sh. Sato, in his article “マドリッド日本人学校における漢字学習指導とその実践” developed a method for teaching hieroglyphs to students studying at the Japanese Language Center located in Madrid, Spain. In accordance with this, he taught hieroglyphs in figurative images and considered teaching methods using interactive games in the lesson [5; –pp.110].

L. M. Rasiban, a researcher at the Faculty of Japanese at the Indonesian Medical University, paid special attention to the method of mnemonics in effective teaching of Japanese characters. In his opinion, learning with the help of mnemonics helped a lot to understand the semantic meaning of each hieroglyph and interpret it correctly. Even students approved of this situation, and the process of mnemonic learning was considered fun and interesting [6; - part 22].

Stefan's article puts forward ideas for teaching Japanese characters based on mnemonics.

According to research by professors of the University of Auckland E. Manalo, S. Mizumi, J. Trafford, teaching Japanese characters using mnemonics facilitates the learning process. The study was conducted among 27 Japanese language learners at the elementary level. The Japanese alphabets hiragana, katakana and kanji (hieroglyphs) are explained using mnemonic cards and stories based on them. As a result, students performed exercises of any level, even additional ones, with special interest.

According to P. Tael and T. Hammonds, it was considered effective to teach hieroglyphic drawing by dividing it into parts using a computer system. In his opinion, by comparing a hieroglyph of a certain elementary level with another hieroglyph close to it in form, the order of writing each hieroglyph and the logical scheme of other hieroglyphic words formed on their basis were created.

E. V. Burtseva in the article "The relevance of memorizing hieroglyphs by students in modern conditions of access to the global information space" believes that effective memorization of hieroglyphs through the use of computer technology in teaching will greatly help to open up new sides of the educational process and make the lesson more enjoyable.

At the University of Tsukuba, Ito Hideaki "Methods of teaching hieroglyphs based on a plot using computer simulation models", researchers at the Centre for Information Technology at Nagoya University, L. Norman, K. Shoji, M. Kenji, developed a textbook called "Method of teaching hieroglyphs based on a mnemonic story". Such works are very important for easy and easy memorization and effective use of hieroglyphic words in the Japanese language.

Researchers at Nagoya University N. Lin, Sh. Kajita, K. Maselar have developed a method for effective teaching of Japanese characters. Accordingly, the Japanese characters studied with the help

of a computer system are explained by creating a mnemonic plot. In this system, each hieroglyphic form is created based on a step-by-step story, starting with the form of its origin, and the connection of the entire part is described by hyperbole. The imagery (audio) of hieroglyphs is expressed with the help of sound, its meaning and with the help of a mnemonic plot. The main attention is paid to the implementation of the studied material using multimodels, that is, audio and video models. In our opinion, the combination of mnemonic storytelling, audio, video and mobile equipment is the most useful and new direction of teaching hieroglyphs based on a computer system.

S. Librenyak, K. Vukovich, Z. Doven in their work “Multimedia assisted learning of Japanese kanji characters” believe that it is possible to implement a system of teaching hieroglyphs for students studying Japanese abroad through multimedia. He gathered 6 students into a group and taught hieroglyphic words for one semester using only multimedia methods, namely websites, videos and smartphones. As a result, the group achieved a high result – successfully mastered 300-400 kanji. On the contrary, the existing difficulties in the course of the previous lesson were solved with pleasure.

In the work of Tsuda University lecturer S. Mayumi in the study of Japanese characters, he believed that it was advisable to continue studying the Japanese language by forming the existing morphemic concept in hieroglyphs from the initial stage.

Conclusion

This is due to the fact that learning the skills of hieroglyphics-kanji-morphemic units from the initial level helps to make the process of understanding hieroglyphs more interesting and understandable for students. Until now, when teaching hieroglyphs, attention has been paid mainly to its semantic part, and a number of scientific innovations have been achieved in this area, but when teaching students these unusual signs, along with its semantic part, morphemic units with many reading methods from the most elementary level will help students learn this language. He thought it would increase his passion again.

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